

Research Article

Study of Efficiency of Some Finite Population Variance Estimators in Stratified Random Sampling

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Abstract

In this paper, six estimators of finite population variance under stratified random sampling have been proposed. The expression for Mean Squared Errors (MSEs) of the proposed estimators was derived up to a first order approximation using the Taylor's series expansion. The empirical study was conducted to compare the efficiency of the proposed estimators and the results revealed that the proposed estimators are more efficient than the other estimators considered in the study.

Keywords: Estimator, Mean Square Error, Efficiency, Stratified Sampling, Finite Population, Variance

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Introduction

The use of supplementary (auxiliary) information, being constant with unit (e.g. population mean, population standard deviation, e.t.c.) or unit free constant (e.g. Coefficient of variation, Kurtosis, e.t.c.), can enhance the efficiency at the estimation stage. Ahmed *et al.* (2000), Gupta and Shabbir (2008), Kadilar and Cingi (2006, 2006a, 2006b), Singh and Solanki (2013), Subramani and Kumarapandiyam (2012 & 2015), Tailor and Shrama (2012), Upadhyaya and Singh (1999), and Yadav and Kadilar (2013a, 2013b) utilized this concept to improve the efficiency of ratio and product type

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estimators for estimating the population mean as well as population variance of study variable. In many real life situations, population units of the variables of interest are often segregated by factors like geographical factors (topology, location, distance, weather), social factors (gender, age, qualification, tribe, level), economic factors (income, salary expenditure, family size) etc which make the population units be heterogeneous in nature (Cochran 1977). In such situations, estimators of finite population variance which assumed homogeneity of population units based on simple random sampling cannot be applied. For instance, the works of Isaki (1983), Upadhyaya and Singh (2006), Kadilar and Cingi (2007), Audu *et al.* (2016) assumed homogeneity of population units based on simple random sampling. In this paper, some estimators of finite population variance are transformed using stratified random sampling scheme to suit any population of interest whose units are characterized by varying attributes.

Sample variance, s_y^2 of study variable is used as an estimator of finite population variance under stratified random sampling S_{yst}^2 is:

$$s_{yst}^2 = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^2}{n_h} \left(\frac{1}{n_h - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} (y_{ih} - \bar{y}_h)^2 \right) \tag{1.1}$$

And its variance is given as

$$Var(s_{yst}^2) = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^3} S_{yh}^4 (\mathbb{E}_{40h} - 1) \tag{1.2}$$

Prasad and Singh (1992) proposed unbiased estimators of finite population variance using auxiliary information in sample survey as follows:

$$S_{PS(st)}^{\wedge 2} = \sum_{h=1}^L \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} \left(s_{y(h)}^2 - \frac{S_{X(h)}^2}{S_{X(h)}^2} + 1 \right) \tag{1.3}$$

$$MSE \left(S_{PS(st)}^{\wedge 2} \right) \cong \sum_{h=1}^L \frac{(W_h S_{y(h)})^4}{n_h^3} \left[(S_{2y(h)} - 1) + \frac{(S_{2x(h)} - 1)}{S_{y(h)}^4} - 2 \frac{(n_{2(h)} - 1)}{S_{y(h)}^2} \right] \tag{1.4}$$

Shabbir and Gupta (2010) proposed some ratio-type estimators of finite population variance of the stratified sample mean as follows:

$$S_{Pi(st)}^{\wedge 2} = \sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{W_h^2}{n_h} \right) \left[r_{1h} s_{y(h)}^2 - r_{2h} \left(\frac{S_{X(h)}^2}{S_{X(h)}^2} - 1 \right) \right] \left(\frac{y_h S_{X(h)}^2 + \%_0 h}{y_h S_{X(h)}^2 + \%_0 h} \right) \tag{1.5}$$

($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$) where r_{1h} and r_{2h} are suitably chosen constants and y_h and $\%_h$ are known population parameters of auxiliary variable which may be $S_{2X(h)}$, $C_{X(h)}$ or $\%_{22(h)}$.

The expression of Mean Square Error (MSE), up to first order of approximation, is as:

$$MSE \left(\hat{S}_{Pi(st)}^2 \right) = \sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} \right) \frac{S_y^4 \left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1) \right) \left(\frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots_h^2) \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1) \right) + \left(\frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots_h^2) \right)} \quad (1.6)$$

Grover (2010) proposed estimator which was on improvement in variance estimation using auxiliary information as follows:

$$\hat{S}_{P(st)}^2 = \sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{W_h^2}{n_h} \right) \left[k_{1h} S_{y(h)}^2 + k_{2h} (S_{X(h)}^2 - s_{X(h)}^2) \right] \exp \left(\frac{S_{X(h)}^2 - s_{X(h)}^2}{S_{X(h)}^2 + s_{X(h)}^2} \right) \quad (1.7)$$

Where k_{1h} and k_{2h} are any constants.

The minimum MSE is given by;

$$MSE \left(\hat{S}_{P(h)}^2 \right)_{\min} = \frac{\left(\frac{S_{y(h)}^4}{n_h} \right) (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots_h^2)}{\left[1 + \frac{\left(\frac{S_{y(h)}^4}{n_h} \right) (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots_h^2)}{S_{y(h)}^4} \right]} \quad (1.8)$$

$$\frac{\left(S_{2X(h)} - 1 \right) \left\{ \left(\frac{S_{y(h)}^4}{n_h} \right) (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots_h^2) + \frac{S_{y(h)}^4 (S_{2X(h)} - 1)}{16n_h} \right\}}{4 \left[1 + \frac{\left(\frac{S_{y(h)}^4}{n_h} \right) (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots_h^2)}{S_{y(h)}^4} \right]}$$

Nursel (2013) proposed improved estimators of finite population variance in stratified random sampling as follows:

$$\hat{S}_{Ni(st)}^2 = \sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{W_h^2}{n_h} \right) \left[w_{1h} s_{y(h)}^2 + w_{2h} \left(\frac{s_{X(h)}^2}{S_{X(h)}^2} \right)^{x_h} \right] \exp \left[\frac{y_h (S_{X(h)}^2 - s_{X(h)}^2)}{y_h (S_{X(h)}^2 - s_{X(h)}^2) + 2\%_0 h} \right], (i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) \tag{1.9}$$

The minimum mean square is

$$MSE_{\min} \left(\hat{S}_{Ni(h)}^2 \right) = S_{y(h)}^4 \left[1 - \frac{BD^2 - DGF + AG^2}{(4AB - F^2)} \right], \tag{1.10}$$

$$\text{Where } A = \left(1 + \frac{(S_{2y(h)} - 1)}{n_h} + \dagger_{ih}^2 \frac{(S_{2X(h)} - 1)}{n_h} - 2\dagger_{ih} \frac{(\binom{n}{22(h)} - 1)}{n_h} \right), \tag{1.11}$$

$$B = \left(1 + \left\{ x_h^2 + \dagger_{ih}^2 + x_h (x_h - 1) - 2x_h \dagger_{ih} \right\} \frac{(S_{2X(h)} - 1)}{n_h} \right) \tag{1.12}$$

$$D = \left(-2 + \dagger_{ih} \frac{(\binom{n}{22(h)} - 1)}{n_h} - \frac{3}{4} \dagger_{ih}^2 \frac{(S_{2X(h)} - 1)}{n_h} \right) \tag{1.13}$$

$$G = \left(-2 + \left\{ \dagger_{ih} x_h - x_h (x_h - 1) - \frac{3}{4} \dagger_{ih}^2 \right\} \frac{(S_{2X(h)} - 1)}{n_h} \right) \tag{1.14}$$

$$F = \left(2 + \left\{ x_h (x_h - 1) + 2\dagger_{ih}^2 - 2x_h \dagger_{ih} \right\} \frac{(S_{2X(h)} - 1)}{n_h} + 2 \left\{ x_h - \dagger_{ih} \right\} \frac{(\binom{n}{22(h)} - 1)}{n_h} \right) \tag{1.15}$$

Nomenclatures used in the Study

Y – Study variable

X – Auxiliary variable

$S_{y(h)}^2, S_{x(h)}^2$ – Population mean square for study and auxiliary variables based on N_h units

N – Total population units

N_h – Total number of population units in the h^{th} stratum

n – Sample size for the study

n_h – Sample size for the h^{th} stratum ($h=1,2,3,\dots,L$ or $h=1,2,3,\dots,m$)

$W_h = \frac{N_h}{N}$ – Proportion of the population units falling in the h^{th} stratum (Stratum weight)

Y_{hi} - The value of study variable for the i^{th} unit in the h^{th} stratum, $i=1, 2, \dots, N_h$

$\bar{x}_{(h)}, \bar{y}_{(h)}$ - Sample Means for the h^{th} stratum

$C_{x_{(h)}}, C_{y_{(h)}}$ - Coefficient of variations for the h^{th} stratum

$S_{2(h)}(x) = \mathbb{E}_{04(h)}$ - Coefficient of kurtosis of auxiliary variable for the h^{th} stratum

$S_{2(h)}(y) = \mathbb{E}_{40(h)}$ - Coefficient of kurtosis of study variable for the h^{th} stratum

$$S_{2(h)}(y) = \frac{\tilde{40(h)}}{\tilde{20(h)}^2}, S_{2(h)}(x) = \frac{\tilde{04(h)}}{\tilde{20(h)}^2}, \bar{X}_h = \frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} X_{(h)i}, \bar{Y}_h = \frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} Y_{(h)i}, \bar{x}_h = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} x_{(h)i},$$

$$\bar{y}_h = \frac{1}{n_h} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} y_{(h)i}, \mathbb{E}_{22(h)} = \frac{\tilde{22(h)}}{\tilde{02(h)} \tilde{20(h)}}, \mathbb{E}_{rs(h)} = \frac{\left. \begin{matrix} \} \\ \} \end{matrix} \right\}_{rs(h)}}{\left. \begin{matrix} \} \\ \} \end{matrix} \right\}_{20(h)} \left. \begin{matrix} \} \\ \} \end{matrix} \right\}_{s/2}}, \left. \begin{matrix} \} \\ \} \end{matrix} \right\}_{rs(h)} = \frac{1}{N_h - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (Y_{(h)i} - \bar{Y}_h)^r (X_{(h)i} - \bar{X}_h)^s$$

$$s_{y(h)}^2 = \frac{1}{n_{y(h)} - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} (y_{(h)i} - \bar{y}_h)^2, s_{x(h)}^2 = \frac{1}{n_h - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_h} (x_{(h)i} - \bar{x}_h)^2, S_{y(h)}^2 = \frac{1}{N_h - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (Y_{(h)i} - \bar{Y}_h)^2,$$

$$S_{x(h)}^2 = \frac{1}{N_{(h)} - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} (X_{(h)i} - \bar{X}_h)^2, x_h = \frac{1}{n_h},$$

Proposed Estimators

Motivated by Audu *et al.* (2016) estimators and having studied some estimators under stratified random sampling, the following estimators are proposed to estimate the population variance of the variable of interest by utilizing the known value of the population parameter of auxiliary variable.

$$\dagger_{1(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} s_{y(h)}^2 k_{h1} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2}{s_{x(h)}^2} \right) \tag{2.1}$$

$$\dagger_{2(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} s_{y(h)}^2 k_{h2} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 - C_{x(h)}}{s_{x(h)}^2 - C_{x(h)}} \right) \tag{2.2}$$

$$\dagger_{3(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} s_{y(h)}^2 k_{h3} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 - S_{2(h)}(x)}{s_{x(h)}^2 - S_{2(h)}(x)} \right) \tag{2.3}$$

$$\dagger_{4(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} s_{y(h)}^2 k_{h4} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 S_{2(h)}(x) - C_{x(h)}}{s_{x(h)}^2 S_{2(h)}(x) - C_{x(h)}} \right) \tag{2.4}$$

$$\dagger_{5(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} s_{y(h)}^2 k_{h5} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 C_{x(h)} + S_{2(h)}(x)}{s_{x(h)}^2 C_{x(h)} + S_{2(h)}(x)} \right) \tag{2.5}$$

$$\dagger_{6(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} s_{y(h)}^2 k_{h6} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 + S_{2(h)}(x)}{S_{x(h)}^2 + S_{2(h)}(x)} \right) \quad (2.6)$$

Properties of the Proposed Estimators (MSEs)

Under this section the bias and mean square error have been derived up to first order of approximation (Table 1).

In order to obtain the Bias and MSE, we defined $e_{0(h)} = \frac{s_{y(h)}^2 - S_{y(h)}^2}{S_{y(h)}^2}$ and $e_{1(h)} = \frac{s_{x(h)}^2 - S_{x(h)}^2}{S_{x(h)}^2}$

such that
$$\left. \begin{aligned} E(e_{0(h)}) = E(e_{1(h)}) = 0, E(e_{0(h)}^2) = \chi_{(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) \\ E(e_{1(h)}^2) = \chi_{(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1), E(e_{0(h)}e_{1(h)}) = \chi_{(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2.7)$$

$$e_{0(h)} = \frac{s_{y(h)}^2 - S_{y(h)}^2}{S_{y(h)}^2}, s_{y(h)}^2 = S_{y(h)}^2 + e_{0(h)} S_{y(h)}^2, s_{y(h)}^2 = (1 + e_{0(h)}) S_{y(h)}^2 \quad (2.8)$$

$$e_{1(h)} = \frac{s_{x(h)}^2 - S_{x(h)}^2}{S_{x(h)}^2}, s_{x(h)}^2 = S_{x(h)}^2 + e_{1(h)} S_{x(h)}^2, s_{x(h)}^2 = (1 + e_{1(h)}) S_{x(h)}^2 \quad (2.9)$$

Expressing equation (2.1) in term of error terms

$$\dagger_{1(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} k_{h1} (1 + e_{0(h)}) S_{y(h)}^2 \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2}{(1 + e_{1(h)}) S_{x(h)}^2} \right) \quad (2.10)$$

Simplify (2.10) up to first order approximation, it reduces to

$$\dagger_{1(st)} - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 k_{h1} (1 - e_{1(h)} + e_{1(h)}^2 + e_{0(h)} - e_{0(h)}e_{1(h)}) - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 \quad (2.11)$$

Square (2.11), take expectation and apply the results of (2.7), obtained $MSE(\dagger_{1(st)})$ as

$$MSE(\dagger_{1(st)}) = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left[\begin{aligned} &(k_{h1} - 1)^2 + k_{h1}^2 \chi_h (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) + \chi_h (3k_{h1}^2 - 2k_{h1}) (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) \\ &- 2\chi_h (2k_{h1}^2 - k_{h1}) (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \end{aligned} \right] \quad (2.12)$$

To obtain the expression for the value of k_{h1} , differentiate $MSE(\dagger_{1(st)})$ partially with respect to k_{h1} and equate to zero

$$k_{h1}^{opt} = \frac{1 + [(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1)]}{1 + [3(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 4(\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) + (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1)]} \quad (2.13)$$

$$MSE(\ddagger_{1(st)})_{\min} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{\left(1 + \chi_h \left[(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \right] \right)^2}{1 + \chi_h \left[3(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 4(\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) + (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) \right]} \right) \quad (2.14)$$

Where $P_{h1} = 1 + \chi_h \left[(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \right]$,

$Q_{h1} = 1 + \chi_h \left[3(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 4(\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) + (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) \right]$

(2.2), (2.3), (2.4), (2.5) and (2.6) can be written as

$$\ddagger_{i(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 k_{h_i} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 A_{h_i} - B_{h_i}}{S_{x(h)}^2 A_{h_i} - B_{h_i}} \right) \quad (2.15)$$

Table 1: Values of A_{h_i} and B_{h_i} in proposed estimators

Estimator	A_{h_i}	B_{h_i}
$\ddagger_{2(st)}$	1	$C_{x(h)}$
$\ddagger_{3(st)}$	1	$S_{2(h)}(x)$
$\ddagger_{4(st)}$	$S_{2(h)}(x)$	$C_{x(h)}$
$\ddagger_{5(st)}$	$C_{x(h)}$	$S_{2(h)}(x)$
$\ddagger_{6(st)}$	1	$-S_{2(h)}(x)$

where $t_{2(h)} = \frac{S_{x(h)}^2}{S_{x(h)}^2 - C_{x(h)}}$, $t_{3(h)} = \frac{S_{x(h)}^2}{S_{x(h)}^2 - S_{2(h)}(x)}$, $t_{4(h)} = \frac{S_{x(h)}^2 S_{2(h)}(x)}{S_{x(h)}^2 S_{2(h)}(x) - C_{x(h)}}$,

$t_{5(h)} = \frac{S_{x(h)}^2 C_{x(h)}}{S_{x(h)}^2 C_{x(h)} - S_{2(h)}(x)}$, $t_{6(h)} = \frac{S_{x(h)}^2}{S_{x(h)}^2 + S_{2(h)}(x)}$,

Express (2.15) in term of error terms

$$\ddagger_{i(st)} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} (1 + e_{0(h)}) S_{y(h)}^2 k_{h_i} \left(\frac{S_{x(h)}^2 - B_{h_i}}{(1 + e_{1(h)}) S_{x(h)}^2 - B_{h_i}} \right) \quad (2.16)$$

Simplify (2.16) up to first order approximation, have

$$\ddagger_{i(st)} - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 k_{hi} \left(1 + e_{0(h)} - t_{i(h)} e_{1(h)} + t_{i(h)}^2 e_{1(h)}^2 - t_{i(h)} e_{0(h)} e_{1(h)} \right) - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^2}{n_h} S_{y(h)}^2 \quad (2.17)$$

$$MSE(\ddagger_{i(st)}) = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left[\begin{aligned} &(k_{hi} - 1)^2 + k_{hi}^2 X_h (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) + t_{i(h)}^2 k_{hi}^2 X_h (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) + 2k_{hi} t_{i(h)}^2 X_h (k_{hi} - 1) \\ &(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 2k_{hi} t_{i(h)} X_h (k_1 - 1) (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) - 2k_{hi}^2 t_{i(h)} X_h (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \end{aligned} \right] \quad (2.18)$$

Square (2.17), take expectation and apply the results of (2.7), obtained $MSE(\ddagger_{i(st)})$ as

$$MSE(\ddagger_{i(st)}) = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left[\begin{aligned} &(k_{hi} - 1)^2 + k_{hi}^2 X_h (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) + t_{i(h)}^2 k_{hi}^2 X_h (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) + 2k_{hi} t_{i(h)}^2 X_h (k_{hi} - 1) \\ &(\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 2k_{hi} t_{i(h)} X_h (k_1 - 1) (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) - 2k_{hi}^2 t_{i(h)} X_h (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \end{aligned} \right] \quad (2.19)$$

To obtain the expression for the value of, differentiate $MSE(\ddagger_{i(st)})$ partially with respect to k_{hi} and equate to zero

$$MSE(\ddagger_{i(st)})_{\min} = \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{\left(1 + X_h \left[t_{i(h)}^2 (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - t_{i(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \right] \right)^2}{1 + X_h \left[3t_{i(h)}^2 (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 4t_{i(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) + (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) \right]} \right) \quad (2.20)$$

Where $P_{hi} = 1 + X_h \left[t_{i(h)}^2 (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - t_{i(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) \right]$, where $i = 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$

$$Q_{hi} = 1 + X_h \left[3t_{i(h)}^2 (\mathbb{E}_{04(h)} - 1) - 4t_{i(h)} (\mathbb{E}_{22(h)} - 1) + (\mathbb{E}_{40(h)} - 1) \right]$$

Efficiency Comparisons

i. Comparison of Sample Variance with Proposed estimators

$$Var(s_{yst}^2) - MSE(\ddagger_{i(st)}) > 0 \quad \text{where } i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^3} S_{yh}^4 (\mathbb{E}_{40h} - 1) - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} \right) > 0 \quad (2.21)$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} > \sum_{h=1}^m W_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4 - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{W_h^4}{n_h^3} S_{yh}^4 (\mathbb{E}_{40h} - 1) \quad (2.22)$$

If condition (2.22) is satisfied, the proposed estimators are more efficient than Sample variance

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ii. Comparison of Stratified Regression Estimator with Proposed Estimators

$$Var\left(\widehat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) - MSE\left(\dagger_{i(st)}\right)_{\min} > 0 \quad \text{where } i = 1,2,3,4,5,6$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L \frac{(W_h S_{y(h)})^4}{n_h^3} (S_{2y(h)} - 1)(1 - \dots_h^2) - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}}\right) > 0 \quad (2.23)$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L (W_h S_{y(h)})^4 \left(\frac{1}{n_h^2}\right) \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} > \sum_{h=1}^m w_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4 - \sum_{h=1}^L \frac{(W_h S_{y(h)})^4}{n_h^3} (S_{2y(h)} - 1)(1 - \dots_h^2) \quad (2.24)$$

If condition (2.24) is satisfied, the proposed estimators are more efficient than Stratified Regression Estimator.

iii. Comparison of Prasad and Singh (1992) Stratified Estimator with Proposed Estimators

$$MSE\left(\widehat{S}_{PS(st)}^2\right) - MSE\left(\dagger_{i(st)}\right)_{\min} > 0 \quad \text{where } i = 1,2,3,4,5,6$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L \frac{(W_h S_{y(h)})^4}{n_h^3} \left[(S_{2y(h)} - 1) + \frac{(S_{2x(h)} - 1)}{S_{y(h)}^4} - 2 \frac{(S_{2(h)} - 1)}{S_{y(h)}^2} \right] - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}}\right) > 0 \quad (2.25)$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L (W_h S_{y(h)})^4 \left(\frac{1}{n_h^2}\right) \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} > \sum_{h=1}^L (w_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4) - \sum_{h=1}^L (W_h S_{y(h)})^4 \left(\frac{1}{n_h^3}\right) \left((S_{2y(h)} - 1) + \frac{(S_{2x(h)} - 1)}{S_{y(h)}^4} - 2 \frac{(S_{2(h)} - 1)}{S_{y(h)}^2} \right) \quad (2.26)$$

If condition (2.26) is satisfied, the proposed estimators are more efficient than Prasad and Singh (1992) Stratified Estimator.

iv. Comparison of Shabbir and Gupta (2010) Estimator with Proposed Estimators

$$MSE\left(\widehat{S}_{Pi(st)}^2\right) - MSE\left(\dagger_{i(st)}\right)_{\min} > 0 \quad \text{where } i = 1,2,3,4,5,6$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{W_h^4}{n_h^2}\right) \frac{S_y^4 \left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1)\right) \left(\frac{1}{n_h} (S_{2y(h)} - 1)(1 - \dots_h^2)\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1)\right) + \left(\frac{1}{n_h} (S_{2y(h)} - 1)(1 - \dots_h^2)\right)} - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}}\right) > \quad (2.27)$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L (w_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4) \left(\frac{1}{n_h^2} \right) \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} > \sum_{h=1}^L (w_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4) - \sum_{h=1}^L (w_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4) \left(\frac{1}{n_h^2} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1) \right) \left(\frac{1}{n_h} (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots^2_h) \right) \quad (2.28)$$

$$\frac{\left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1) \right) \left(\frac{1}{n_h} (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots^2_h) \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{n_h} \dagger_{ih}^2 (S_{2X(h)} - 1) \right) + \left(\frac{1}{n_h} (S_{2y(h)} - 1) (1 - \dots^2_h) \right)}$$

If condition (2.28) is satisfied, the proposed estimators are more efficient than Shabbir and Gupta (2010) Stratified Estimator.

v. Comparison of Grover (2010) Estimator with Proposed Estimators

$$MSE\left(\hat{S}_{P(h)}^2\right) - MSE\left(\dagger_{i(st)}\right)_{\min} > 0 \quad i = 1,2,3,4,5,6$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} \left(\frac{\text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right)}{\left[1 + \text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) / S_{y(h)}^4\right]} - \frac{\left(S_{2X(h)} - 1\right) \left\{ \text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) + S_{y(h)}^4 \left(S_{2X(h)} - 1\right) / 16n_h \right\}}{4 \left[1 + \text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) / S_{y(h)}^4\right]} \right) \quad (2.29)$$

$$- \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} \right) > 0$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} > \sum_{h=1}^L w_h^4 \left(S_{y(h)}^4 - \frac{\text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right)}{n_h^2 \left[1 + \text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) / S_{y(h)}^4\right]} \right. \quad (2.30)$$

$$\left. + \frac{\left(S_{2X(h)} - 1\right) \left\{ \text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) + S_{y(h)}^4 \left(S_{2X(h)} - 1\right) / 16n_h \right\}}{4n_h^2 \left[1 + \text{var}\left(\hat{S}_{Reg(h)}^2\right) / S_{y(h)}^4\right]} \right)$$

If condition (2.30) is satisfied, the proposed estimators are more efficient than Grover (2010) Stratified Estimator.

vi. Comparison of Nursel (2013) Estimators with Proposed Estimators

$$MSE\left(\widehat{S}_{Ni(h)}^2\right)_{\min} - MSE\left(\dagger_{i(st)}\right)_{\min} > 0 \quad i = 1,2,3,4,5,6$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^L \left(\frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2}\right) S_{y(h)}^4 \left[1 - \frac{BD^2 - DGF + AG^2}{(4AB - F^2)}\right] - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}}\right) > 0 \quad (2.31)$$

$$\sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \frac{P_{hi}^2}{Q_{hi}} > \sum_{h=1}^m w_h^4 S_{y(h)}^4 - \sum_{h=1}^m \frac{w_h^4}{n_h^2} S_{y(h)}^4 \left(1 - \frac{BD^2 - DGF + AG^2}{(4AB - F^2)}\right) \quad (2.32)$$

If condition (2.32) is satisfied, the proposed estimators are more efficient than Nursel (2013) Estimator.

Empirical Study

In this section, efficiency of proposed estimators is compared to that of existing estimators using real life data

Results of real Life Data

Data 1: Nursel (2013)

y: leaf area for the newly developed strain of wheat, x: weight of leaves

N=39, n=14, N₁=12, N₂=13, N₃=14, n₁=4, n₂=5, n₃=5, C_{x1}=0.1118928, C_{x2}=0.0733753, C_{x3}=0.1193784, S_{y1}=6.0664603, S_{y2}=5.2915229, S_{y3}=6.4961301, S_{x1}=11.5715804, S_{x2}=8.139014, S_{x3}=12.4494617, S_{2(y₁)} = 1.9394547, S_{2(y₂)} = 2.9819269, S_{2(y₃)} = 2.3448986, S_{2(x₁)} = 2.2748233, S_{2(x₂)} = 3.436904, S_{2(x₃)} = 2.8955496, }₂₂₍₁₎ = 1.9123464, }₂₂₍₂₎ = 2.970998, }₂₂₍₃₎ = 2.5134376

Data 2: Kadilar and Cingi (2005)

Y= Level of apple production, X=Rate of apple trees, Strata=Villages

N=854, n=140, N₁=106, N₂=106, N₃=94, N₄=171, N₅=204, N₆=173, n₁=9, n₂=17, n₃=38, n₄=67, n₅=7, n₆=2, C_x=3.85, C_{x1}=2.02, C_{x2}=2.10, C_{x3}=2.22, C_{x4}=3.84, C_{x5}=1.72, C_{x6}=1.91, S_y=171.6, S_{y1}=64.25, S_{y2}=115.52, S_{y3}=299.07, S_{y4}=286.43, S_{y5}=23.90, S_{y6}=9.46, S_x=1447.94, S_{x1}=491.89, S_{x2}=574.61, S_{x3}=1607.57, S_{x4}=2856.03, S_{x5}=454.03, S_{x6}=187.94, }_{2(y)} = 195.84, }_{2(y₁)} = 80.13,

S_{2(y₂)} = 97.68, S_{2(y₃)} = 24.14, S_{2(y₄)} = 101.97, S_{2(y₅)} = 53.38, S_{2(y₆)} = 27.96, S_{2(x)} = 312.07, ... = 0.92
S_{2(x₁)} = 25.71, S_{2(x₂)} = 34.57, S_{2(x₃)} = 26.14, S_{2(x₄)} = 97.60, S_{2(x₅)} = 27.47, S_{2(x₆)} = 28.10, ...₁ = 0.82,
...₂ = 0.86, ...₃ = 0.90, ...₄ = 0.99, ...₅ = 0.71, ...₆ = 0.89, w₁ = 0.21, w₂ = 0.12, w₃ = 0.11, w₄ = 0.20,
w₅ = 0.24, w₆ = 0.20. }₂₂ = 0.6, }₂₂₍₁₎ = 33.30, }₂₂₍₂₎ = 57.40, }₂₂₍₃₎ = 20.80, }₂₂₍₄₎ = 99.53,
}₂₂₍₅₎ = 21.09, }₂₂₍₆₎ = 23.08,

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Table 2: MSE of Proposed and some Related Estimators using Data 1

Estimator	Efficiency Condition	Bias	MSE	PRE
Sample Variance	$\Phi > 43.72699$	0	0.649830316	100
Prasad and Singh (1992)	$\Phi > 50.99746$	0	0.613226536	105.969047
Regression	$\Phi > 51.27363$	0	0.116676239	556.951717
Grover (2010)	$\Phi > 12.41696$	-0.11327	0.094564711	687.180566
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_1	$\Phi > 51.16868$	-0.12739	0.106589594	609.656432
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_2	$\Phi > 51.15737$	-0.12683	0.106211405	611.827248
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_3	$\Phi > 48.06202$	-0.12977	0.108249991	600.305192
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_4	$\Phi > 51.10579$	-0.12682	0.106203465	611.872989
Shabbir and Gupta (2010) P_5	$\Phi > 48.72394$	-0.12739	0.106540528	609.937202
Nursel (2013) N_1	$\Phi > 49.81454$	-0.18241	0.156913494	414.132844
Nursel (2013) N_2	$\Phi > 49.81425$	-0.17278	0.149461117	434.782189
Nursel (2013) N_3	$\Phi > 49.94941$	-0.25758	0.214113793	303.497643
Nursel (2013) N_4	$\Phi > 49.81229$	-0.17257	0.149292451	435.273392
Nursel (2013) N_5	$\Phi > 49.8945$	-0.18106	0.155862965	416.924133
Proposed † _{1(st)}	$\Phi = 51.31254$	-0.1363815	0.06148141	1056.95415
Proposed † _{2(st)}	$\Phi = 51.31254$	-0.1372025	0.05330264	1219.13345
Proposed † _{3(st)}	$\Phi = 51.31254$	-0.1630484	0.05330262	1219.1339
Proposed † _{4(st)}	$\Phi = 51.31254$	-0.1366703	0.05292946	1227.72897
Proposed † _{5(st)}	$\Phi = 51.31254$	-0.0040334	0.05038629	1289.69669
Proposed † _{6(st)}	$\Phi = 51.31254$	-0.1288795	0.05255186	1236.55055

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Table 3: MSE of Proposed and some Related Estimators using Data 2

Estimator	Efficiency Condition	Bias	MSE	PRE
Sample Variance	$\Phi > 12036055$	0	5606.121	100
Prasad and Singh (1992)	$\Phi > 12036056$	O	5605.534	100.0105
Regression	$\Phi > 12041045$	O	616.7009	909.0502
Grover (2010)	$\Phi > 3623.667$	-2.42e+16	207.9835	2695.464
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_1	$\Phi > 12040428$	906.0566	718.2054	780.5735
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_2	$\Phi > 12040428$	906.6814	719.1967	779.4976
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_3	$\Phi > 10990678$	-288432.1	617.1637	908.3686
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_4	$\Phi > 12028187$	-3039.779	670.7554	835.7922
Shabbir and Gupta (2010) P_5	$\Phi > 1203126$	-480472.3	617.0774	908.4956
Nursel (2013) N_1	$\Phi > 12041516$	0.3641395	194.4375	2883.251
Nursel (2013) N_2	$\Phi > 12040770$	0.1195034	199.8611	2805.009
Nursel (2013) N_3	$\Phi > 1204133$	-0.6661212	177.0669	3166.103
Nursel (2013) N_4	$\Phi > 14042108$	1.466432	143.3661	3910.353
Nursel (2013) N_5	$\Phi > 52106.82$	0.5079666	121.067	4630.594
Proposed $\ddagger_{1(st)}$	$\Phi = 12041603$	-23.32184	49.60071	11302.5
Proposed $\ddagger_{2(st)}$	$\Phi = 12041603$	-27.95439	49.60064	11302.52
Proposed $\ddagger_{3(st)}$	$\Phi = 12041603$	-27.9523	49.59987	11302.69
Proposed $\ddagger_{4(st)}$	$\Phi = 12041603$	-27.95493	49.60077	11302.488
Proposed $\ddagger_{5(st)}$	$\Phi = 12041603$	-27.95657	49.60112	11302.41
Proposed $\ddagger_{6(st)}$	$\Phi = 12041603$	-27.96686	49.60155	11302.31

Data 3: Elements of Sampling Survey.

Y= The number of refrigerators expected sales for the current summer (CS)

X=The number of refrigerators sold during last summer (LS)

The whole country is divided into 4 zones (4 Strata)

$N=1254, N_1=400, N_2=216, N_3=364, N_4=274, n=42, n_1=14, n_2=9, n_3=12, n_4=7,$
 $C_x= 0.048731709, C_{x1}=0.036343313, C_{x2}=0.05837041, C_{x3}=0.040438375, C_{x4}=0.042029466,$
 $S_y=15.53999, S_{y1}=12.91157586, S_{y2}=13.2014309, S_{y3}=15.05344016, S_{y4}=12.16161017,$
 $S_x=15.05848, S_{x1}=14.52943205, S_{x2}=14.03962646, S_{x3}=13.89217133, S_{x4}=13.06212263,$

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${}_{2(y)}=2.668867921, {}_{2(y_1)}=3.0698777, {}_{2(y_2)}=1.4337019, {}_{2(y_3)}=2.5422223, {}_{2(y_4)}=2.1207669,$
 $S_{2(x)}=1.970676267, S_{2(x_1)}=2.0434422, S_{2(x_2)}=2.0422387, S_{2(x_3)}=1.799631, S_{2(x_4)}=1.6393728,$
 $\dots_1=0.7810, \dots_2=0.8891, \dots_3=0.9004, \dots_4=0.899,$
 $\}{}_{22}=1.866173088, \}{}_{22(1)}=1.682704795, \}{}_{22(2)}=1.34534583, \}{}_{22(3)}=1.767674308, \}{}_{22(4)}=1.527675842,$

Table 4: MSE of Proposed and Some Related Estimators Using Data 3

Estimator	Efficiency Condition	Bias	MSE	PRE
Sample Variance	$\Phi > 728.1473$	0	0.7212271	100
Prasad and Singh (1992)	$\Phi > 728.1732$	O	0.6952795	103.732
Regression	$\Phi > 728.6877$	O	0.1808174	398.8704
Grover (2010)	$\Phi > 675.2649$	6906.82	0.1819532	396.3806
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_1	$\Phi > 728.6953$	-0.186862	0.1819442	396.4002
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_2	$\Phi > 728.6923$	-0.1908343	0.1819318	396.4272
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_3	$\Phi > 728.7059$	-1.779404	0.1687389	427.422
Shabbir and Gupta(2010) P_4	$\Phi > 728.5153$	-0.2077627	0.1818796	396.541
Shabbir and Gupta (2010) P_5	$\Phi > 728.7022$	-1.797352	0.1736502	415.3333
Nursel (2013) N_1	$\Phi > 723.5213$	-0.007539884	5.347244	13.48783
Nursel (2013) N_2	$\Phi > 728.8201$	-0.006977832	7.750028	9.306123
Nursel (2013) N_3	$\Phi > 728.6584$	-0.006834163	7.763422	9.290067
Nursel (2013) N_4	$\Phi > 728.8231$	-0.004742593	7.73789	9.320721
Nursel (2013) N_5	$\Phi > 724.6191$	-0.0058743	5.347244	13.48783
Proposed $\dagger_{1(st)}$	$\Phi = 728.8234$	-0.354629	0.1549662	465.4093
Proposed $\dagger_{2(st)}$	$\Phi = 728.8234$	-0.3547142	0.1549704	465.3967
Proposed $\dagger_{3(st)}$	$\Phi = 728.8234$	-0.3584108	0.1552109	464.6755
Proposed $\dagger_{4(st)}$	$\Phi = 728.8234$	-0.3546841	0.1549682	465.4033
Proposed $\dagger_{5(st)}$	$\Phi = 728.8234$	-0.301479	0.1518736	474.8864
Proposed $\dagger_{6(st)}$	$\Phi = 728.8234$	-0.3527674	0.1547337	466.1086

Tables 2-4 showed Bias, MSE and PRE of the proposed and some related estimators using data 1, 2 and 3 respectively. From the results of Tables 2-4 it is clear that all the estimators considered in the study are biased with exception of sample variance, Prasad and Singh (1992) and Regression estimators. The results also show that the proposed

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estimators have minimum MSE compare to that of other related estimators considered. Conditions for the efficiency of proposed estimators over other estimators were also satisfied. Table 2-4 also show that all the proposed estimators are equally efficient in all the three population data sets.

Conclusion

From the results of empirical studies conducted using real life data, the results revealed that the efficiency conditions of the proposed estimators over other related estimators considered in the study were satisfied. The results also show that the proposed estimators have minimum MSE and higher PRE compared to other estimators considered in all the numerical computations carried out in the study. Conclusively, the results of the empirical study revealed that the proposed estimators are more efficient that other estimators considered in the study, that is, the proposed estimators have higher chances of producing estimate that is closer to the true values of finite population variance than other estimators.

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